

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

2024-25 Seed Grant Program Final Report

Developing 3D P-Wave and S-Wave Seismic Attenuation Models for the Mendocino Triple Junction Region Using Double-Difference Attenuation Tomography with Onshore and Offshore Data

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20512766>

U.S. National
Science Foundation

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Developing 3D P-Wave and S-Wave Seismic Attenuation Models for the Mendocino Triple Junction Region Using Double-Difference Attenuation Tomography with Onshore and Offshore Data

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1. Abstract

The Mendocino Triple Junction (MTJ) region, one of the most seismically active regions in Cascadia, is of high priority for ground motion modeling and seismic hazard assessment. Seismic attenuation, represented by seismic quality factor Q and characterizing subsurface anelasticity, is a critical parameter for more accurate simulations of scenario earthquake ground motions and assessing seismic hazards from potential moderate and large earthquakes and for understanding the physical processes governing the coupling and rheology of the megathrust fault. The goal of this project is to develop a high-resolution three-dimensional (3D) seismic attenuation model for the MTJ region using local onshore and offshore earthquake data and the advanced double-difference seismic attenuation (DDQ) tomography method. We have determined a new P-wave seismic attenuation (Q_p) model using the DDQ tomography method with absolute t^* and differential t^* data extracted from the spectra and spectral ratio data from local earthquakes recorded on local onshore and offshore stations. Thanks to the combined onshore and offshore data, our new Q_p model is well resolved from the deformation front to more than 200 km eastward into the onshore region. The subducted Gorda slab is generally imaged as a low- Q body but has significant variations in Q within the slab crust. The slab crust shows low- Q values in the highly locked zone at depths of ~ 10 -20 km and in the episodic tremor and slow slip (ETS) zone at depths of ~ 30 -40 km, while the transition zone in between shows high Q . These suggest downdip variations in porosity and fluid content from the locked zone to the ETS zone. The overlying North America crust shows lateral variations in Q that are consistent with the geological structures. Multiple low- Q channels connecting the overlying crust and the subducted slab are imaged and may serve as pathways of upward fluid migration. Therefore, our 3-D Q model helps to advance our understanding of spatial variations in material properties within and above the subducted slab in the MTJ region, particularly the distribution of fluids. Such a high-resolution Q model will be also valuable for more accurate simulations of earthquake ground motions.

2. Data and Methodology

We used data from 3,185 local earthquakes recorded by permanent and temporary seismic stations deployed in both the onshore and offshore parts of the MTJ region (Fig. 1). The offshore data were collected from two dense ocean bottom seismometer (OBS) arrays deployed during 2012-2015 as a part of the Cascadia Initiative (CI) experiment (Toomey et al., 2014). The onshore data were collected from permanent seismic networks, i.e., stations from Northern California Earthquake Data Center NCEDC (NCEDC, 2014), temporary land stations deployed during the CI experiment, and a temporary network XQ deployed during 2007-2009 (Levander, 2007).

We used the DDQ tomography method (Guo & Thurber, 2021; Guo & Thurber, 2022) to determine a 3D seismic attenuation model. The general concept of the DDQ tomography is similar to the widely used double-difference velocity tomography method of Zhang & Thurber (2003). DDQ tomography contains three elements: first extract absolute t^* data (t^* is the attenuation operator along the whole ray path) from earthquake spectra using a single spectrum inversion method that jointly solves for source and attenuation parameters; then extract the event-pair differential t^* data (dt^* : t^* difference from two events recorded by a common station) from earthquake spectra ratio data using a joint spectral ratio inversion method that jointly solves for source parameters and dt^* ; and finally conduct a tomography inversion with t^* and dt^*

data to determine a 3-D Q model. Compared to traditional Q tomography methods using absolute t^* data only (e.g., Eberhart-Phillips & Chadwick, 2002), DDQ tomography can image higher-resolution Q structures in seismically active regions (Guo & Thurber, 2021). We used data from vertical component for P-wave analysis and from two horizontal components for S-wave analysis. It is also noteworthy that we used the latest 3-D velocity model of the MTJ region to find ray paths and calculate travel times, which are required and fixed during the Q tomography inversion. This velocity model was originally developed by Guo et al. (2021) and recently updated by PI Guo under the support of the Statewide California Earthquake Center (SCEC).

3. Results

We have completed the P-wave DDQ tomography and the S-wave DDQ tomography is still in progress. Fig. 2 shows an along-dip cross-section of our new Q_p model along with the latest V_p , V_s , and V_p/V_s models and relocations of regular earthquakes and low-frequency earthquakes (LFEs) that PI Guo has determined recently through local earthquake tomography. Note that the LFEs were detected by Plourde et al. (2015) and relocated by PI Guo. We conducted checkerboard test to assess model resolution and masked low-resolution regions. In Fig. 2, the slab interface, represented by the solid red line, is approximately estimated based on relocations of regular earthquakes and LFEs and velocity and Q models. We also assume that the slab crust, outlined by the solid and dashed red lines, is about 6 km thick. The slab is generally imaged as a high- Q_p and low- V_p/V_s body but has significant downdip variations within slab crust. The slab crust shows low Q_p and high V_p/V_s in the locked zone at depths of ~10-20 km and low Q_p and low V_p in the ETS zone at depths of 30-40 km (V_p/V_s is poorly resolved in the ETS zone). In comparison, the transition zone between the locked and ETS zones shows increased Q_p and decreased V_p/V_s . These may suggest high porosity and fluid content in the locked zone and the ETS zone while the transition zone has low porosity and fluid content, same as the inference of Guo et al. (2021) based on their V_p/V_s model. The inferred decreased porosity from the locked zone to the transition zone may accompany the brittle-to-ductile transition, which is primarily caused by increased temperature (Beeler et al., 2016; Gao & Wang, 2017). The increased porosity and fluid content from the transition zone to the ETS zone is likely a result of fluids from slab dehydration being trapped at the top of the slab (Peacock et al., 2011). Near-lithostatic fluid pressures near the mantle wedge corner in Cascadia could significantly lower the brittle strength to values below the ductile strength and thus are responsible for the occurrence of tectonic tremors, LFEs, and short-term slow slip events in this region (Beeler et al., 2016; Gao & Wang, 2017). The overlying North America crust shows lateral variations in attenuation and velocity structures with increased Q_p and decreased V_p/V_s from the Franciscan complex to the Klamath terrane (Beaudoin et al., 1996). Multiple high- V_p/V_s and low- Q_p anomalies connecting slab crust and the overlying continental crust are imaged and may serve as channels of upward fluid migration. Therefore, our high-resolution Q model along with the latest velocity model provides strong constraints on spatial variations in material properties within and above the subducted slab, especially the distribution of fluids, which are critical for better understanding megathrust coupling. Such a high-resolution attenuation model will be also valuable for earthquake ground motion modeling.

4. Future Work

We will finalize our Q_p model and interpretations and prepare a manuscript for publication in a peer-review journal, such as JGR-Solid Earth. Our final Q_p model will be archived in the openly accessed repository Zenodo. We will continue to work on and complete the S-wave DDQ tomography of the MTJ region. Another longer-term plan is to extend our DDQ tomography work farther north from the MTJ region to cover the entire Cascadia subduction zone.

Figure 1. Earthquakes and seismic stations in the MTJ region used for our DDQ tomographic inversion. Dots and squares represent regular earthquakes and low-frequency earthquakes (LFEs), colored by focal depths. Triangles represent onshore and offshore seismic network stations, as labelled in the legend. The black sawtooth line represents the deformation front. Gray lines represent depth contours of the Gorda slab interface from the Slab2 model (Hayes et al., 2018). The Mendocino Fault and San Andreas Fault are shown as black lines. The thick black line trending NNE direction from the deformation front to the east of LFEs represents the profile of the cross-section shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Along-dip cross-sections of the latest V_p , V_s , and V_p/V_s models, our new Q_p model, and locations of regular earthquakes and LFEs. The thick black line in Fig. 1 shows where the profile is. Earthquakes within 5 km of the profile and LFEs within 20 km of the profile are shown as black and green dots, respectively, and only the earthquakes used for our DDQ tomographic inversion are shown. The approximate ranges of the locked zone, the transition zone, and the ETS zone are shown at the top of the figure. We placed dashed lines at the top and bottom of the locked zone to emphasize that the locking state at the shallow part of the megathrust, primarily offshore, and the exact location of the downdip end of the fully/highly locked zone are not well constrained. We manually outlined the top of slab interface with the solid red line. The solid red line and the dashed red line (6 km below the solid red line) outline the slab crust, assuming the slab crust is 6 km thick. In the V_p/V_s and Q_p cross-sections, the geological structures at the top of the North America crust are approximately outlined, including the accretionary wedge, the Franciscan stratum, and the Klamath stratum. Green arrows represent potential channels of upward fluid migration. Black triangle, the deformation front; thin black line near the surface, bathymetry and topography. The regions with poor resolution estimated from checkerboard tests are masked.

5. Presentations

- Guo, H. (2025, 10). Imaging Along-Dip Variations in Material Properties of the Subducted Crust and Their Link to Megathrust Fault Coupling in Southern Cascadia. Oral Presentation at 2025 CRESCENT Offshore Observations Topical Workshop, Incoming Structure Session, held at the University of Washington, Seattle.
- Guo, H. (2025, 10). Downdip variations in material properties of the subducted Gorda slab crust near Mendocino Triple Junction from high-resolution seismic tomography. Poster Presentation at 2025 CRESCENT Annual Meeting held at the University of Washington, Seattle.

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